

GUDUMMUWAR RUBUTACCEN ADABI WAJEN FARFAƊO DA KIMAR NIJERIYA

By

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Abstract

The research titled, Gudummuwar Rubutaccen Adabi Wajen Farfado da Kimar Nijeriya was aimed at identifying the causes of bad image of Nigeria as portrayed by the other countries. The research x-tray causes of the bad image and provide suggestions as possible solutions to the problem indentified. The bad image of Nigeria has become an issue of discussion almost every day, both in and outside the country this is as a result of high-level corruption, indiscipline, unpatriotism, injustice, election malpractice and other related vices perpetuated by the leaders and even some followers. This paper is of the view that Hausa Written Literature especially prose and poetry can play a significant role in re-branding the image of Nigeria. This through sensitization or educating the people on how to tackle the problems mentioned. Book like "Nagari Na Kowa" written by Jabir Abdullahi and Tura Ta Kai Bango by Suleiman Ibrahim Katsiina will be used and poems of Mudi Spikin, Salihu Kwantagora would also be used. The research finds out that bribery and corruption, misappropriation of public funds and desperation in accession of money, examination malpractice, ridging of elections, cultism and ritual money among other things are causes of bad in Nigeria. Therefore, it recommends leaders should try as much as possible to be fair and justice in deals with subjects. Hard working should be rewarded and any other forms of malpractice identified such be punished.

Key words: Rubutaccen adabi, Nijeriya, Tubali, Kima

Gabatarwa

Nijeriya a matsayin ƙasa mai ƙarfin tattalin arziki da yawan jama'a da suke da ƙima da mutunci a idanun duuniya, musamman a zamanin mulkin shugabanni irin su Sir Abubakar Tafawa Balewa da Chief Nmadi Azikwe da Sir Ahmadu Bello Sardaunan Sakkwato da Chief Obafemi Awolowo, da Janar Gowonn da Murtala Mohammed da Shehu Shagari da dai sauransu. Waɗannan shugabanni su yi adalci da kwatanta gaskiya a lokacin jagorancinsu. Wannan ya haifar wa Nijeriya ƙima a idon duniya. Hakan ya sa ba a yi duk wani ɗan Nijeriya wani dogon bincike a duk inda ya tsinci kansa. Dalilin kuwa kuwa shi ne saboda riƙo da gaskiya da adalci ga kowa wanda ya samar da zaman lafiya a cikin al'umma.

A yau ta zamo ƙasar da ake ƙyama da kuma tsoro wanda ya kai har wasu ƙasashe na tababar yiin wata hulɗa da ita. Kyamar ya shafi duk `yan Nijeriya a duk ƙasar da tsinci kansu ana yi masu Kallon azzalumi masarasa ƙima da Daraja. Bayan haka, duk inda suka shiga ana zarginsu da aika wasu miyagin halaye da dabi`u, wanda hakan yana hana su damar samun wasu abubuwa waɗanda suka cancanta sus amu ko kuma yin Daraja da girma da ƙima da ya dace a ce sun samu ko martabar da ya kamata a nuna masu duk ba sus amu.

Wannan ko yana aukuwa ne sanadiyyar matsaloli irin su cin rashawa da ha'inci da zalunci da ƙeta da almuɓazzaranci da rashin tsaro da watanda da dukiyar jama'a da maguɗin zaɓe da rashin wadattaccen ilimi da sauran makamantan haka da miyagun azzaluman shugabanni suka jawo wa ƙasar wannan zubewar ƙima a idon duniya. Matsalolin nan da aka ambata sun zamo ƙaska a cikin zukatan `yan Nijeriya, saboda kowane ɗan Nijeriya yana neman dama ce wadda zai samu ya yi waa tattalin arziƙin ƙasar zagon ƙasa. Dalilin haka ne gwamnatin ƙasar ta samar da hukumomi da kula yi wa tattalin arziƙin ƙasa zagon ƙasa domin kamawa da hukunta masa wannan laifi.

Wanda hakan ya sa a yau, yana da matuƙar wuya ka iya canza akalar tunanen ɗan Nijeriya ta hanyar nuna masa cewa zai iya zama wani abu, ba tare da ya yi watanda da dukiyar jama'a ba. Irin wannan tunanin ne, yake sanya wasu faɗawa cikin wasu miyagun halaye na rayuwa kamar su sace-sace da barayin daji da masu

satar mutane suna garkuwa da su shiga kungiyoyin asiri da kashe-kashe da zamba cikin aminci da zama `yan barandan siyasa da sauran makamantan hakan. Wadannan halaye sun jefa Nijeriya a cikin mummunar matsala ta tattalin arziƙi, tare gurgunta ƙasa da zubar mata da ƙima a idon duniya.

A taƙaice, wannan muƙala za ta tattauna mana irin rawar da rubutaccen adabin Hausa musamman ƙagaggun labarai da kuma waƙoƙi za su taka wajen farfado da martabar Nijeriya. Ta hanyar gargadi da faɗakarwa da wayar da kan jama'a kan abubuwan da suka jawo taɓarbarewar mutuncin Nijeriya da kuma `yan Nijeriya. Littafin Tura Ta Kai Bango da Nagari Na Kowa suna daga cikin waɗannan da za a kafa hujja da su.

Rubutaccen Adabi

Rubutaccen adabi yana nufin adabin da aka shirya a ka, aka kuma aiwatar da shi ta hanyar amfani da alƙalami da takarda, wanda tarihin samuwarsa abu ne da za a iya kididdigewa.

A taƙaice, dai adabi ne da bai samu ba sai bayan da Hausawa suka sadu da baƙin al'umma wato Larabawa da kuma Turawa. Shi ya sa ma ake yi masa laƙabi da “Adabin Zamani”.

Masana irin su Dangambo (1984) da Dalhatuu da Yahaya (1986) da Malumfashi (2001) da Yakuubu (2005) da Bunza (1996) da Gusau (2008) sun kasa rubutaccen adabi zuwa gida uku kamar haka: Zube da waƙa da kuma wasan kwaikwayo.

Kowane daga cikin ukun nan, yana taka muhiimmiyar rawa wajen wayar da kan jama'a da tarbiyya da raya al'adu da faɗakarwa da bunƙasa ilimi da koyar da dabarun zaman duuniya da kuma gyaraAn hali da dai sauran makamantan haka (Dangambo 1984:44).

Damgane da wannan muƙala za mu taƙaita aikinmu ne a kan rubutaccen zube da kuma ruubutattun waƙoƙi.

Rubutun Zube A Matsayin Tubalin Farfado da Kinar Nijeriya

Rubutun zube kamar yadda na faɗa a baya, yana ɗaya daga cikiin nau' o' in adabin zamani (Rubutacce) kuma yana ba da muhimmiyar gudummuwa wajen rayuwar al'umma.

Shi dai rubuutun zube kamar yadda Muktar (2004) da Yahaya (1988) da Dangambo (1984) da Gusau (2008) da Malunfashi (2009) suka bayyana yana nufin uk wani rubuutu da ba waƙa ba kuuma ba wasan kwaikwayo ba, wato tsagwaron rubutu kai tsaye wanda aka yi shi cikin shafi ko shafuka da sakin layi daban-daban a rubuce. Ire-iren waɗannan rubutun sun haɗa da littafin Ruwan Bagaja da littafin Shehu Umar da Littafin Nagari Na Kowa da kuma littafin Tura Ta Kai Bango da Magana Jari Ce da dai sauransu.

Wannan nau' i na adabin zamani yana taka rawa kuma zai taka muhimmiyar rawa, wajen farfaɗo tare da dawo da martabar `yan Nijeriya a idon duniya. Musamman ma, a wannan lokaci da ha'inci da zalunci da cin amana da yi wa doka hawan kawara da rrashin adalci da zamba cikin aminci da maguɗin zaɓe da rashin tsaro da dai sauran makamantansu suka yi katutu a cikin kasar ba ga shugabanni ba, ba kuma ga talakawa ba, wanda irin waɗannan ɗabi' u da halaye suna jawo zubewar mutuncin Nijeriya a idon wasu ƙasashe har ya kai suke ƙyamar yin wata hulɗa da mutanen Nijeriya domin sau da yawa wasu suna Kallon `yan Nijeriya a matsayin mazambata `yan (419) kuma azzalumai.

Sannan a cikin kasar ga tauye haƙin mai ƙaramin ƙarfi da shugabanni suke yi da a za kansu a kan gwamnatin ta hanyar maguɗin zaɓe da mai da shari'a ba bakin komai ba, duk irin waɗannan idan aka dubi darussan da ke a cikin wasu ƙagaggun labarai aka kuma yi aiki da su, to, hakan zai taimaka wajen dawo da martabar Nijeriya. Ga dai wani misali daga littafin Nagari Na Kowa da Jabir Abdullahi ya rubuta.

A cikin littafin marubucin ya nuna muhimmancin riƙe gaskiya inda ya nuna duk wanda ya tsaya wa gaskiya to babu shakka, duniya za ta so shi kuma zai yi nasara. A inda Jabiru ya ɗauki halin Danduna da na Salihi da su zama abin kwatance da koyi, Danduna ya ce wa ɗansa:

“Ina so in ƙara tuna maka cewa har abada
kada rikikitar al' amurran duniya ta ba ka
tsoro, kai dai kullum ka tsaya bisa tafarkin

gaskiya ka da kuwa ka yarda a kwar da
kai daga gare shi (Shafi na 91)

Ka ga wannan nasiha ce mai matuƙar muhimmanci wadda ake da kishin irinta a yau a Nijeriya musamman idan aka yi la'kari da irin halin da ake ciki. Babu shakka amfani da irin wannan nasiha za iyi tasiri matuƙa wurin saita al'amura su daidaita.

Haka a wani wuri marubucin ya bayyana abubuwan da suka dami duuniya, wanda in har aka ci nasarar kwar da su to duniya za ta yi kyau.

Wannan matsalar tai daidai da abubuwan da ke aukuwa yau a Nijeriya ga dai abin da yake cewa:

“Ina amfanin sanin mutum kome wayonsa
Idan yana tare da rrashin gaskiya da hasada
Da cin amana da keta da sonn kai da
Almubazzaranci da dai sauransu da yawa
(Shafu na 93).

A taƙaice, dai wannan littafin yana koƙarin fadakarwa ne kan muhimmancin riƙo da halayen kirki da tsare tafarkin gaskiya duk yadda aka daka aka raya, sannan kuma yana jawo hankali tare da aikata wasu munanan abubuwa irin su: rashin gaskiya da hasada da cin amana da keta da son kai da almubazzaranci da dai sauran ayyukan assha. Komai ilimin mutum, komai sanin mutum, matuƙar yana aikata waɗannan miyagun halaye ba zai taɓa kasancewa mai daraja da kima ba.

A nan idan muka dubi wannan da idon basira sai mu ga cewa, kamar marubucin ya tsara wannan littafin ne kacokan a kan halin da Nijeriya take ciki a yau. Idan `yan Nijeriya za su dɒuki halayen kwarai na cikin wannan littafi su aikata su ana da yaƙinin to, ko shakka babu, martabar Nijeriya za ta dawo kamar yadda aka san ta. In ko, aka ci gaba da tafiya a kan miyagun abubuwa, to, al'amarin zai kara taɓarbarewa ne.

Haka kuma. Idan muka koma ta fuskar zaɓe bisa la'akari da abubuwan da suke wakana a yau na maguɗin zaɓe da amfani da karfi wurin tursasa wa talakawa ba su abin da ba su zaɓa ba, to, sai ga cewa littafin Tura Ta Kai

Bango na Suleiman Ibrahim Katsina za ya taka muhimmiyar rawa wajen yakar wannan dabi'ar, matuƙar za a yi aiki da darrussan ko abubuwan da ya kawo a cikin littafin.

A cikin littafin ya nuna irin yadda `yan jari hujja suke yaudarar talakawa ta hanyar yi masu alƙawurran karya da amfani da kuɗi wurin sayen kuri`u da satar kuri`a don cin zaɓe da sauran makamantar haka.

Hakazalika, marubucin ya nuna muna, yadda `yan addawa suka yi ta ƙoƙarin wayar da kan talakawa don su fahimci gaskiya su zaɓar wa kansu abin da zai fissa su.

Da tura ta kai bango marubucin ya nuna muna yadda talakawa suka fito kansu da kwarkwata wajen yakar `yan jari hujja ta hanyar jifarsu da kuma yi masu a bure wanda hakan ya ba su damar samun nasara wajen canza gwamnatin danniya zuwa ga sabuwar gwamnatin da za ta share masu hawaye. Ga dai abin da marubucin yake cewa a cikin littafin:

“Ga shi dai talakawa sun sha jifar su duk inda aka je lacca, ga shi kuma yau kamar dukkan talakawan ma`aikatan Jam`iyyar sauyi ne, hhar aka ƙare zaɓe, talakawa ba su yarda da wani wand aba a sani bay a jefa kuri`a, ba su kuma ba su yarda wani ya je rumfar da ba ta unguwarsu ba. Ba su yarda da soma jefa kuri`a ba, sai an buɗe akwati kowa ya gani ba kommi ciki. Matsara akwattin da suke ma wayau, yanzu kar suke. Da kowa sai su tsya a yi ta ƙare. Haka ma, masi kirga, ba su yarda `Yansanda ko Soja su kore su ba. Idanunsu kamar na shaho. Iska bay a tasowa ba tare da sun dub aba. Wannan irin tashi tsaye, lallai bana Tura Ta Kai Bango (Shafi na 90)”

Yayin da talakawa suka samu nasarar kafa gwamnatin da suka zaɓa sai suka gaa gaggarumin canji na ci gaba kamar dai yadda ya zo a littafin:

“Daga yau ilimi ya koma kyauta, kuma dole ga yaron da ya kai shekara shida zuwa bakwai daga Firamare har zuwa Jami`a. babu sauran biyan kuɗi a asibiti ko da na kati ne. kana babu wani mutum shi ɗaya da zai hamdame fili mai yawa ya ce nasa ne shi kaɗai, ƙasa duk ta duk waɗanda ke wahala a doronta ne”.

Wannan shi ne a taƙaice, irin rawar da wannan littafi ya taka wajen wayar da kan talakawa da hankaltar da su a kan yadda za su yaƙi maguɗin zaɓe don samun gwamnatin adalci wanda kuma suka samu nasarar yin haka.

Ashe ke nan idan talakawa Nijeriya za su yi koyi da abin da wannan littafi ke nunawa, to za su iya dawo da martabar zabe su kuma daga darajar Nijeriya a idon duniya.

A ta'kaice, idan muka dubi saƙonin da waɗannan littattafan suke dāuke da shi bisa abin da muka gani a cikin wannan aikin za mu yarda mu kuma amince da cewa rubutaccen adabin Hausa ta fuskar zube, zai taimaka wajen farfado da martaba tare da mutuncin Nijeriya a idanun duniya muddin dai za a karanta a yi amfani da darussan da suke koyarwa.

Idan muka koma ta fuskar waƙa, za mu ga cewa su ma, marubuta waƙoƙin Hausa suna taka muhiimmiyar raawa wajen wayar da kan jama'a tare da faɗakar da su a kan abin da zai jawo masu kariyar mutunci da martaba, dama dai, waƙa wata hanya ce ta isar da saƙo cikin kanƙanin lokaci, cikin hikima a kan abin da ya shafi rayuwar al'umma (Bayero, 1997).

Bisa wannan ne, nika da ra'ayin cewa, rubutattun waƙoƙin Hausa za su taka rawa wajen dawo da martabar Nijeriya a idon duniya. Waƙar Malam Salihu Kwantagora mai suna, "Waƙar Hana Zalunci" tana dāya daga cikin waɗannan waƙoƙin, domin waƙa ce, da ta tattauna aibun zalunci. Ga dai abin da marubucin yake cewa:

“Ina mai fatawa ya zo gunka,
Ya ce mene ne zalunci?
Shaida masa yanke ka bar tsoro,
Sabawa tafarkin adalci.
Da zamowa mai karamin karfi,
Gun mai karfi wainar cinci.
Karbar rashawa kyautar hanci,
Kirga shi ga kunshin zalunci.
To kun ga waɗannan munanan,
Abubuwa su ne zalunci.”

Haka shi ma Mudi Spikin a cikin wata waƙarsa mai suna, "Karara" ya kawo abubuwan da ke bata mutuncin kasa wanda in aka bar su to kasa za ta yi kyau. Ga kaɗan daga abin da yake cewa:

“Mu wo himma mu tashi tsaye,
Mu gyara kasa ta san 'yanci.
Idan ba tattali a kasa,

Haƙiƙa dole ta ɓaci.
Idan kuma ba tausayi a ƙasa,
Mutane na ta makirci.
Idan kuma har amana tai
Ƙaɗan sai nuna hha'inci.
Idan a ƙasa akkwai wannan,
Haƙiƙa dole ta ɓaci.

Ka ga duk kasar da take so ta riƙe martabarta da mutuncinta, to, dole ta kauce wa waɗannan ɗabi'un. Don haka, waƙoƙi su ma tubalai ne na dawo da martabar Nijeriya matuƙar za a yi amfani da saƙon da suke ɗauke da shi.

Shawarwari

Martaba da mutuncin kowace irin al'mma, bai samuwa da kuma tsayuwa sai an kawar da zalunci da ha'inci da haɗama da yin babakere da dukiyar jama'a. a kan haka ne nika kira ga shugabannin Nijeriya da su ji tsoron Allah su tsaya wa gaskiya su kuma yi adalci wajen jagirantar al'ummar da suke shugabanta.

Haka kuma su kuma talakawa, su yi koƙarin kauce wa amfani da shugabanni suke yi don biyan buƙatansu a kan ba su abin da bai taka kara ya karya ba.

Har-ila-yau, ina mai ba da shawara a yawaita karanta irin waɗannan littattafan da kuma waƙoƙin a makarantunmu na Firamare da Sakandare har zuwa Kwalejoji da Jami'o'I tare da yin aiki da abin da suka nazarta.

Kammalawa

Wannan muƙala ta tattauna irin rawar da adabin Hausa rubutacce musamman na littattafan zube da kuma waƙoƙi suke takawa wajen yaƙar zalunci da rashin gaskiya da maguɗin zaɓe da sauran makamantansu. Wanda hakan zai taimaka wajen farfaɗo da martabar Nijeriya a idon duniya, musamman ganin cewa su ne suka yi karati a cikin wannan ƙasa da ya sa a yau, Daraja da kimarta suka raunanan a idon duniya.

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